

A Comparative Study of Networking Link Enhancement Algorithms

Chyan Yang, Levent Misirlioglu
Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering
Naval Postgraduate School
Monterey, California 93943-5004

Abstract

Link enhancement provides a better routability and hence survivability of a communication network. Though the problem is NP-complete good heuristics do exist that can provide near-optimal solutions with negligible computation time. A closer investigation of different heuristics shows the merit of each approach. Annealing process is investigated to explore the potential improvement at negligible marginal computation time. This paper presents the algorithms, and discuss the performance of annealing algorithms.

1 Introduction

Network survivability has been studied mainly for the purpose of establishing fault-tolerant networks. Many researchers have studied the subject based on concepts in graph theory that relate to either spanning trees [1, 2] or cutsets [3]. To achieve the balance between affordability and survivability, parameterized by the number of circuits required, a linear programming model is also used to minimize total cost for a communication system [4]. The specific problem of each research may be different and the corresponding optimal solution to that problem can be proven intractable. Realizing the difficulty of the problems, several researchers have proposed heuristic approaches for solving network survivability problems [5, 6, 7].

It is common that an existing network consisting of many nodes, will contain some nodes that are directly connected with communication links while some of them have to communicate indirectly through immediate nodes. Sometimes, it is desirable to add communication links between nodes of a communication network enhancing the network routability and survivability [1, 2]. For an existing computer network it is important and interesting to ask the question:

what is the optimal link enhancement for a given investment? Our purpose is to maintain a maximum communication network survivability and achieve the performance requirement.

The link enhancement problem is NP-complete [7]. Generally speaking, we should find an algorithm that provides near-optimal solution and takes non-exponential time to compute [4]. In this paper we present three algorithms, two of which are previously studied, and each latter algorithm contributed the problem at the expense of some additional computation time.

2 Linear Search Algorithms

Linear search algorithms have been reported and detailed examples can be found in [7]. Its basic idea is to search the sorted table until the budget is exhausted.

All the heuristic algorithms discussed in [7] has the advantage that, since sorting can be done in $O(n \log n)$ time we can achieve our solution in $O(n \log n)$ time. Unfortunately, even with 6 heuristic algorithms to choose from, the Linear Search Algorithms do not have a high probability of reaching optimality. But they build a very useful base for CRCS algorithms.

3 Improvement by Constrained Range and Reduced Candidate Set

Two major improvements can be done over the linear search algorithms : constrained range (CR) and reduced candidate set (RCS). These algorithms is worked in detail in [9] and greatly improved the Linear Search Algorithm solutions. The basic ideas are given below.

39.4.1

3.1 Constrained Range and Squeezing the Constrained Range

Given a budget, B , and costs of candidate links, c_i , we may find the optimum solution within a constrained range hence saving computational costs. Let C_{min} and C_{max} be the minimum and the maximum c_i respectively. Notice that with the given B we can readily compute the constraints: the upper limit, $UL = \lfloor B/C_{min} \rfloor$, and the lower limit LL defined as

$$\begin{cases} LL = \lfloor B/C_{max} \rfloor & \text{if } FS_c(n-l) \leq r \\ LL = \lfloor B/C_{max} \rfloor & \text{if } FS_c(n-l) > r \end{cases}$$

where $r = B - \sum_{i=n-l+1}^n FS_c(i)$ and $l = \lfloor B/C_{max} \rfloor$ and FS_c denotes the sorted list of the links in cost ascending order. LL indicates the number of links we can increase when all the budget is used for the links that each requires C_{max} . In a practical sense, this is the minimum number of links we can add. The ceiling in the LL expression represents the possibility that the leftover of B/C_{max} may be sufficient for yet another link. If this possibility is void, the floor option is chosen for conservative computation. UL , however, represents the number of links that we can increase when all of the budget is used for the links that each requires C_{min} . UL is the maximum number of links we can add. The floor in the UL expression represents the impossibility that the leftover of B/C_{min} can be used for any other link since no link costs less than C_{min} . The LL and UL give us the range that the optimum solution should lie: $[LL, UL]$ instead of $[0, n]$. In practice, once we obtain the solution from linear algorithms we can squeeze this constrained range further and greatly reduce the computation time.

The maximum number k that satisfies

$$\sum_{i=1}^k FS_p(i) < P_{linear}$$

may squeeze the LL further. Here FS_p denotes the sorted list of links in profit descending order and P_{linear} is the maximum profit obtained by Linear Search Algorithms. If the best k choices of $FS_p(i)$ cannot beat the P_{linear} then we are sure that LL should be no smaller than k . By the similar scenario, the maximum number k that satisfies

$$\sum_{i=1}^k FS_c(i) \leq B$$

may squeeze the UL further: $UL = \min(UL, k)$. In other words, if the best k choices of $FS_c(i)$ is very close to B such that no more link can be added then we are sure that UL must be no greater than k .

3.2 Reduced Candidate Set

The philosophy behind the RCS is that if a link should be in the optimal solution set this link must have a high probability to be selected by one of the linear search algorithms. In other words, if we want to improve the result from the linear search algorithms all we need is to examine only those links that have been selected by the linear search. This method, the RCS, rejects links that may or may not be in the optimal solution set therefore it may not reach the optimal solution. Hopefully, the gain in this heuristic is justified by both shorter computation time and higher probability of reaching optimality.

4 Annealing Process

We have seen from previous work that CRCS algorithm compromise in trading computation time for the possibility of losing optimality [9]. Among 3960 cases already tested, 30 could not reach optimal solution. To reach optimality, among those 30 cases, 22 cases need only one, 7 cases need two, 1 case needed three links to be replaced.

The chance of losing optimality is a function of the set of the links that are excluded when generating Reduced Candidate Set (RCS). Let us call the set of the excluded links as ECS (Excluded Candidate Set) for further reference.

With CRCS algorithm we have reached a high possibility of finding optimal solution (99.24%)[9]. With CRCS as the base algorithm we determine whether there is a way to improve its solution by replacing r link(s). This process is called " $(r+1)$'s Chance" algorithm. The name explains the idea behind the algorithm: before committing to a solution one has a choice to replace r links in the current solution set. The feasibility of improving a CRCS solution is dictated by the remaining budget and the costs changes when substituting links. The algorithm gives a chance to each group of ' r ' link to be in the optimal solution set. This process is a simulated annealing process that will be further explained.

4.1 What is Annealing Process ?

Simulated annealing [10] is a technique for obtaining approximate solutions to combinatorial optimization problems. The execution of the simulated annealing algorithm requires specification of the following quantities:

- A data structure representing the solution space: We will use the set of solutions found by CRCS algorithm, S_{CRCS} as the solution space.
- A cost function whose differences can preferably calculated incrementally: Our cost evaluation function is based on the differences between c_i 's and p_i 's of particular group of links
- A neighborhood structure representing for each solution the set of feasible solutions that can be reached in one single step: The set of Excluded Candidates (ECS) forms the neighborhood structure.
- A cooling schedule : $(r+1)^{st}$ Chance process itself is the cooling procedure.
- All possible tuples are generated by taking the product of the solution set and ECS.
- Two measures, $\Delta Cost = c_i - c_j$, and $\Delta Profit = p_i - p_j$ are computed for each tuple, where i and j indicate the elements from the solution set and ECS respectively.
- If for any tuple $\Delta Cost < \Delta Budget$ and $\Delta Profit > 0$ then i^{th} element in the solution set is replaced by the j^{th} element in the ECS.
- If more than one tuple satisfies the condition above, the tuple with maximum $\Delta Profit$ is selected.

Thus it is possible for us to use the Simulated Annealing Techniques for Link Enhancement Problem. The evaluation of a trial will be consisted of the following four tasks.

- Selecting a new solution from the neighbors of the current solution
- Calculating the difference in cost between these two solutions
- Deciding whether or not the new solution is to be accepted
- Replacing the current solution by the new solution if the new solution is to be accepted

4.2 Second Chance Algorithm

For this study we have examined 'r = 1' case (second chance) in detail. The second chance algorithm can be extended to higher degrees. Second chance algorithm is a simple, first order annealing process and is the most cost effective method for the following reasons:

- 73% of the unsuccessful cases of CRCS algorithm require only one link to be changed in achieving optimality (maximal benefit).
- The algorithm looks for the new links only in the ECS (minimal additional cost).

Specifically, the following procedures constitute the annealing process:

- Compute $\Delta Budget = (Budget - Budget\ used)$.

This process guarantees to change one link if the change provides better solution.

4.2.1 Examples

Example 1

This interesting example was taken from the previous work. It is a case where CRCS algorithm can not find the optimal solution. We will use it to show the potential benefits from annealing process. In one case of $n = 23$ listed in Table 1 the budget is $B = 11500$. The best linear search algorithm gives the contribution of 37768. The candidate set formed by linear search algorithms has 20 links to be considered and $RCS = \{1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 23\}$. The constrained range can be obtained as $LL = B/C_{max} = 11500/1498 = 7$ and $UL = B/C_{min} = 11500/693 = 16$. A further squeeze of the range reduces both LL and UL to 12. Examining combinations of 12-out-of-20 from the RCS, we can improve the solution $S_{CRSC} = \{18, 17, 15, 13, 12, 11, 8, 7, 5, 4, 3, 1\}$ with the contribution of 37815. Unfortunately, the exact optimal solution set is $\{18, 17, 15, 13, 12, 11, 8, 7, 5, 4, 2, 1\}$ with a contribution of 37862; this set differs from the S_{CRSC} only by one link. On a VAX 11/780 processor of a single user the CRCS algorithm needs 43 seconds user time for this specific problem while the exact optimal solution requires 693 seconds.

For this example the budget used by the solution set is 11292, $\Delta Budget = 11500 - 11292 = 208$, S_{CRSC} above and $ECS = \{2, 10, 22\}$. Second chance process then executes the iterations tabulated at Table 2 and after 36 iterations finds the optimal solution by replacing link 3 with 2. But the optimal solution has calculated $C(23, 12) - C(20, 12) = 1,226,108$ additional iterations to obtain the same result. The execution

39.4.3

Table 1: $n = 23, B = 11500, Example : 1$

Link No	Cost	Profit	Link No	Cost	Profit
1	796	3191	13	957	3132
2	1225	2963	14	787	2746
3	1066	2916	15	1031	3304
4	847	3104	16	1067	2870
5	1003	2947	17	1082	3127
6	1057	2902	18	1187	3295
7	693	3314	19	1107	2900
8	823	3074	20	964	2812
9	1498	3107	21	1012	2868
10	1242	2824	22	1196	2818
11	891	3140	23	801	2762
12	916	3271	-	-	-

Table 2: Iterations Calculated by Second Chance of Example 1; Links with * are to be replaced $\Delta B = 208$

Link Id	2*		10		22	
	ΔC	ΔP	ΔC	ΔP	ΔC	ΔP
1	429	-228	446	-367	400	-373
3*	159	47	176	-92	130	-98
4	378	-141	395	-280	349	-286
5	222	16	239	-123	193	-129
7	532	-351	549	-490	503	-496
8	402	-111	419	-250	373	-256
11	334	-177	351	-316	305	-322
12	309	-308	326	-447	280	-453
13	268	-169	285	-308	239	-314
15	194	-341	211	-480	165	-486
17	143	-164	160	-303	114	-309
18	38	-332	55	-471	9	-477

time required by Second Chance algorithm is measured to be less than one second.

Example 2

Sometimes Second Chance process could not find the optimal solution. Table 3 shows the case: $n = 29, B = 2900$. The best solution of the linear search is {5, 17, 27}. RCS is relatively small due to insufficient Budget and contains 9 links, {3, 5, 10, 12, 13, 17, 25, 26, 27}. The solution found by CRCS is {27, 12, 5} yielding a total cost of 2833 and total profit of 10303. After 60 iterations, Second Chance process improves the result by replacing link 27 with link 16 and reaching a total profit of 10344 which improves the CRCS solution. But the optimal solution is {27, 15, 16} and differs from

Table 3: $n = 29, B = 2900, Example : 2$

Link number	Cost	Profit	Link number	Cost	Profit
1	1049	2984	16	965	3484
2	1425	3284	17	821	3337
3	759	3050	18	1280	3438
4	1073	2929	19	951	2759
5	827	3348	20	987	2766
6	1068	2953	21	1042	2811
7	895	2772	22	1072	2935
8	1550	3109	23	768	2975
9	769	2973	24	1010	2779
10	1106	3512	25	758	3102
11	1065	2960	26	758	3067
12	1101	3512	27	905	3443
13	798	3288	28	849	2807
14	1036	2803	29	1409	3304
15	925	3459	-	-	-

CRCS solution by two links. So a third chance algorithm would find the optimal solution, by taking $\Delta Cost(\{15,16\},\{5,12\}) = \Delta Cost(cost_{15} + cost_{16}, cost_5 + cost_{12}) = -38$ and $\Delta Profit(\{15,16\},\{5,12\}) = \Delta Profit(profit_{15} + profit_{16}, profit_5 + profit_{12}) = 83$ after 990 iterations, whereas the exact optimum algorithm should make 3,570 iterations. Note that the Second Chance algorithm selects the link 16, though it indeed is in the optimal set, the link it replaces (link 27) is also in optimal set. The Third Chance algorithm, however, does avoid this incapability of Second Chance method and achieve the optimality.

5 Overall Performance Discussion

Time dependent performance analysis of CRCS algorithms is explained in detail in previous work [9]. For this study we have used the same program and data to explore possible improvements by using simulated annealing process. Time requirement for Second Chance algorithm is obviously negligible and indeed the measured elapsed time is less than 1 second for all the tried 3960 cases. What we have shown here is that we can improve our solution by using annealing process, even the first order may provide a 99.79% hit. It can be easily shown that, third order is also not so expensive, so we may reach 100 % for this experimental case. But there will be always other data and other distribution that will beat $r = 3$ case.

6 Conclusion

Link enhancement problems are crucial to network routability and survivability. The problems, however, are NP-complete. Heuristics exist that may provide optimal solutions, in most cases, with significantly less computation time than that of exact optimal solution. The search of constrained restricted candidate set (CRCS) has been proven to be the best known heuristic for solving the link enhancement problems. The annealing process or the $(r+1)^{st}$ chance algorithm can piggy back on a CRCS solution and improves it to the optimal one with negligible incremental computation time.

Acknowledgement

The authors like to thank Gregory M. Whittaker at MITRE for his insights of the problem. His idea of annealing process lead to the result of our experiments.

References

1. Newport, K. T. and Varshney, P. K., 'On the Design of Performance-Constrained Survivable Networks,' *Conference Record, 1989 IEEE Military Communications Conference*, pp. 663-670.
2. Schroeder, M. A. and Newport, K. T., 'Enhanced Network Survivability Through Balanced Resource Criticality,' *Conference Record, 1989 IEEE Military Communications Conference*, pp. 682-687.
3. Wu, Lin and Varshney, P. K., 'On Survivability Measures for Military Networks,' *Conference Record, 1990 IEEE Military Communications Conference*, pp. 1120-1124.
4. Rizik, P. D., 'A Model for Survivable, Low Cost Access Area Network Design in a New Europe,' *Conference Record, 1990 IEEE Military Communications Conference*, pp. 1097-1102.
5. Newport, K. T., Schroeder, M. A., and Wittaker, G. M., 'Techniques for Evaluating the Nodal Survivability of Large Networks,' *Conference Record, 1990 IEEE Military Communications Conference*, pp. 1108-1113.
6. Wittaker, G. M., Schroeder, M. A., and Newport, K. T., 'A Knowledge-Based Approach to the Computation of Network Nodal Survivability,' *Conference Record, 1990 IEEE Military Communications Conference*, pp. 1114-1119.
7. Yang, C and Kung, C, 'Networking Link Enhancement with Minimum Costs,' *Conference Record, 1990 IEEE Military Communications Conference*, pp. 1125-1128.
8. Tirumalai, P. and Butler, J. T., 'Minimization Algorithms for Multiple-Valued Programmable Logic Arrays,' *IEEE Transaction on Computers*, Vol. C-40, No. 2, February 1991, pp. 167-177.
9. C. Yang, 'Link Enhancement Using Constrained Range and Reduced Candidate Set Searches,' *Journal of Computer Communications*, Butterworth Heinemann, to appear.
10. S. Kirkpatrick, C. D. Gelatt Jr and M. P. Vecchi, 'Optimization by Simulated Annealing,' *Science*, 220(1983) pp 671-680.